

**SYMBOLS AND RELIGIOUS AND SPIRITUAL INTERPRETATION
OF ERNEST HEMINGWAY'S PARABLE STORY "THE OLD MAN AND
THE SEA"**

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Abstract: The article analyses the symbols and religious and spiritual interpretation of Ernest Hemingway's parable story "The Old Man and the Sea". It examines the key symbols-the old man, the sea, and the fish-and their relationship to religious and spiritual themes. The use of these symbols to convey profound ideological and philosophical ideas is examined. Particular attention is paid to issues of human endurance, faith and struggle. Offers a new perspective on the tale, revealing the complex religious and spiritual undertones of this work.

Keywords: composition, circular framing, resilience, humility, interpretation, symbolic interpretation.

**ERNEST XEMINGUEYNING "QARIYA VA DENGIZ" HIKOYA-
MASALINING TAHLILINING RAMZIY VA DINIY-MA'NAVIY TALQINI**

Annotatsiya: Maqola Ernest Xemingueyning "chol va dengiz" qissasi-masalining ramzlari va diniy va ma'naviy talqinini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Unda asosiy ramzlar-chol, dengiz va baliq, ularning diniy va ma'naviy mavzular bilan aloqasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu ramzlardan chuqur mafkuraviy va falsafiy g'oyalarni etkazish uchun foydalanish ko'rib chiqiladi. Insonning chidamliligi, e'tiqodi va kurash masalalariga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Ushbu asarning murakkab

diniy va ma'naviy subtekstlarini ochib beradigan voqeaga yangi nuqtai nazar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarkibi, halqali bayon, chidamlilik (sobitlik), kamtarlik, talqin, ramziy talqin.

СИМВОЛЫ И РЕЛИГИОЗНО-ДУХОВНАЯ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ПОВЕСТИ-ПРИТЧИ ЭРНЕСТА ХЕМИНГУЭЯ «СТАРИК И МОРЕ»

Аннотация: Статья посвящена анализу символов и религиозно-духовной интерпретации повести-притчи Эрнеста Хемингуэя “Старик и море”. В ней рассматриваются ключевые символы-старик, море и рыба, и их связь с религиозными и духовными темами. Рассматривается использование этих символов для передачи глубоких идеологических и философских идей. Особое внимание уделяется вопросам человеческой выносливости, веры и борьбы. Предлагается новый взгляд на повесть, раскрывая сложные религиозные и духовные подтексты этого произведения.

Ключевые слова: композиция, кольцевое обрамление, стойкость, смирение, интерпретация, символическая интерпретация.

"The Old Man and the Sea" is one of the most famous works by Ernest Hemingway, which was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature. In this allegorical tale, Hemingway uses biblical motifs to create a complex and profound portrait of an old man fighting against the sea and its inhabitants.

The tale was written in 1951 and consists of a three-part composition with circular framing: "The Old Man and the Boy", "The Old Man and the Fish", "The Old Man's Return".

In analyzing the allegorical tale, numerous references are made to the resilience, humility, will, and aspirations of the main character [1:6,13,24;5:26,32].

Although the author avoided revealing the idea of the work in discussions with critics, insisting only on the desire to realistically depict the state and actions of the fisherman in the prevailing conditions, in this article we will consider a religious-symbolic interpretation of the actions of the main character.

Key Characters: The conditional first part of the composition is associated with the old man and the boy. The boy is named Manolin, which is a diminutive endearing form of Emmanuel, one of the names of Jesus Christ. The old man is named Santiago, which is also the name of St. James, as well as the Biblical Jacob, who wrestled with God. These names accentuate the connection between the characters and biblical figures.

The old man's prayers: In the tale, the old man recites the fundamental Christian prayers - "Our Father" and "Hail Mary".

Symbolism of the fish: The enormous fish that the fisherman battles with carries a dual symbolic significance: on one hand, it is a collective image of all the fish caught by Santiago in the past, a representation of the task ordained to him by God, and on the other hand, it is a depiction of the Creator Himself, dwelling in each of His creations, dying for humanity, resurrecting, and living in the souls of believers.

Overall, the biblical motifs in "The Old Man and the Sea" serve to deepen the character of the old man and his struggles, as well as to create a connection between his life and broader spiritual themes. This makes the tale more complex and profound, allowing readers to see the links between the old man's life, his trials, and biblical figures. It also underscores the universality of themes and ideas that Hemingway explores in his work.

It is also possible to interpret the generalized image of the fisherman:

Apostle Peter: Peter was a fisherman before becoming an apostle of Jesus Christ.

Andrew the Apostle: Andrew was also a fisherman and is one of the most well-known saints whom fishermen often venerate.

Saint Nicholas: In Orthodoxy, Saint Nicholas is considered the patron saint of fishermen and sailors.

Saint Anthony of Padua: This saint is predominantly venerated in Italy. He is considered the patron saint of fishermen and those who live near rivers.

Saint Thomas Aquinas: Fishermen also turn to Saint Thomas Aquinas, possibly due to his role as the patron saint of animals.

For a deeper analysis, the second part of the tale, "The Old Man and the Fish," employs brief excerpts from its content, but the interpretation of the actions, thoughts, and feelings of Santiago is carried out based on early Christian symbols comprising the triad - Cross, Anchor, and Heart. Historians believe these symbols have served as a metaphor for representing the three fundamental Christian values over millennia: faith, hope, and love. Together, they form the symbol of the Holy Trinity [4].

Let's analyze the episodes where Santiago's actions could be characterized by the symbol of an anchor - hope:

Hope for a catch: Santiago, going out to sea, hopes to catch a large fish. He catches a tuna, which gives him hope that a big fish might be swimming nearby.

Hope for victory over the marlin: The old man struggles with a huge marlin, which becomes the biggest catch of his life. This battle lasts for several days, and the old man maintains hope for victory throughout.

Hope for the return with the catch: After defeating the marlin, Santiago ties it to his boat and heads home, hoping he can reach the shore with his catch.

Hope for the boy's help: Santiago is confident that the boy Manolin will fish with him, giving him hope.

Despite all the difficulties and trials, Santiago does not lose hope and continues to fight. This is a key moment in the tale, emphasizing the indomitable spirit of the main character.

In Hemingway's "The Old Man and the Sea," there are significant instances where the main character, Santiago, experiences love, with the symbol of this feeling being the heart:

Love for sea creatures: Santiago shows respect and love for all living beings in the sea. He worries for birds struggling to feed themselves and delights in the playful antics of sea turtles, feeling sorry for and loving them.

Compassion for the marlin: The old man feels compassion for the marlin, which lost its mate because of him. He regards the large fish with a deep sense of respect.

Respect for fish: Every encounter with marine life, Santiago shows respect towards it.

Love for the sea: He compares the sea to a woman and addresses it as "La mar," acknowledging and tolerantly enduring its whims.

Paternal love for the boy Manolin.

These moments underscore Santiago's deep connection with nature and his love for life in all its manifestations.

Similarly, in Hemingway's "The Old Man and the Sea," there are several episodes where the main character, Santiago, demonstrates his faith, with the symbol of this being the cross:

Faith in victory over the marlin: Santiago, battling with the enormous marlin, believes in his victory. This faith helps him not to give up and continue the struggle.

Faith in himself: Despite his old age and loneliness, Santiago believes in his abilities. He is confident that he can overcome all challenges and trials.

Faith in the dream: Santiago dreams of victory, and this dream gives him the strength to continue the fight.

Faith in unity with nature: Santiago feels his connection with nature and believes in its assistance. He talks to fish and birds as living beings and believes in their support.

These moments highlight the unwavering spirit of the main character and his faith in himself and his dreams.

This analysis allows us to see the depth of meanings and symbolism in Ernest Hemingway's work "The Old Man and the Sea." The biblical motifs used by the author add new layers to the piece and allow readers to see the connection between the old man's life and broader spiritual themes. The main character, Santiago, becomes a symbol of resilience, faith, hope, and love. His struggle against the sea and its inhabitants reflects the human struggle with their own trials and tribulations. Various symbols, such as the cross, heart, and anchor, help understand the depth of the feelings and thoughts of the main character. Thus, "The Old Man and the Sea" remains a relevant work that continues to inspire readers and stimulate interest in exploring its symbolism and meanings.

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